

Assessment of Thyroid Function during the First Trimester of Pregnancy in a Group of Women in Gaza, Palestine

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ABSTRACT

Pregnancy is associated with significant but reversible changes in thyroid function. Obstetrical complications are expected in pregnant women with thyroid dysfunction. This study aims to assess the maternal thyroid function during the first trimester in a group of pregnant women in Gaza – Palestine. The present cross sectional study was designed and included 80 pregnant women and 80 non-pregnant as a control group. Thyroid function tests were carried out including serum levels of thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), free thyroxin (FT4), and free triiodothyronine (FT3) using Microparticle Enzyme Immunoassay (MEIA). The results showed an elevated levels of TSH in 2.5 % of both pregnant and non-pregnant women. FT4 showed high level in 1.25 % of pregnant women. FT3 was elevated in 13.75 % and 1.25 % of pregnant and non-pregnant women respectively. The mean values of TSH for both groups were not significant; however, the mean values of FT4 and FT3 were significantly higher in the pregnant women compared to controls. It was concluded that thyroid dysfunction is not uncommon among pregnant women of Gaza. Screening of thyroid function in early pregnancy should be performed to avoid future complications for both fetus and pregnant woman. The relationship between thyroid hormones and other maternal hormones should be assessed.

Keyword: *Thyroid function, pregnancy, Gaza, Palestine.*

INTRODUCTION:

Thyroid dysfunction is common among women of child-bearing age and it may cause complications of pregnancy. It is estimated that 2.5% of all pregnant women have some degree of hypothyroidism [1]. Thyroid function is affected by the physiological state and hormonal changes during pregnancy [2]. For this reason, thyroid function test results should be interpreted with caution [3]. At least two hormones have influence on thyroid function during pregnancy, human chorionic gonadotropin hormone (HCG), and estrogen. High levels of HCG during the first trimester may result in low TSH levels which then return to normal throughout the duration of pregnancy.

Estrogen increases the concentration and half-life of thyroxin binding globulin (TBG) which may subsequently lead to increased thyroxin levels [4,5]. Thyroid disorders may affect both the pregnant woman and the developing fetus as thyroid hormones having a crucial role in embryogenesis and fetal development. During the first 12 weeks of gestation, the fetus is completely dependent on the mother for thyroid hormones [6].

The major target for thyroid hormones are the cells of the brain, its maturation is dependent on a transport protein called organic anion transporter (OATP1C1) which allows T4 to cross the blood brain barrier [7]. Children born to mothers with hypothyroidism during pregnancy had lower IQ and impaired psychomotor development [8]. Uncontrolled thyroid activity is associated with serious fetal problems such as impaired neurological development, low birth weight as well as stillbirth. Maternal complications may include miscarriage, pregnancy – induced hypertension, preterm labor and placental abruption [9].

The most common etiology of hypothyroidism in pregnant women is chronic autoimmune thyroiditis (Hashimoto's thyroiditis), other causes include iodine deficiency [10]. Hyperthyroidism occurs in 0.4% of pregnancies [11], it is defined as serum TSH level is below the trimester specific reference range with elevated levels of FT3 or FT4 or both. The most common cause of hyperthyroidism in pregnancy is Grave's disease, thyrotoxicosis, or excessive hormone intake [9]. The aim of this study was to assess maternal thyroid function in the first trimester for a group of women living in Gaza – Palestine.

Materials and Methods

A cross sectional design was selected to conduct this study. A total of 80 pregnant women were randomly selected, all were in the first trimester of pregnancy, and age range was 18-40 years. The control group comprised 80 apparently healthy non-pregnant with the same age range. A permission to conduct this study was obtained from the local Helsinki committee after observing ethical issues. Blood samples (5 ml.) were collected in plain tubes without anticoagulant, left to clot and then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min., serum was separated and kept at -70 °C until assayed. Biochemical analysis for TSH, FT3 and FT4 were performed using AXSYM full automated immunoassay (Abott Laboratories, U. S. A). A questionnaire was designed to collect relevant data from all subjects. SPSS program was used for statistical analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that age mean for pregnant and control groups were 24.9 and 29.3 years respectively. The average gestational age of pregnant women was 8.7 weeks.

An average pregnancy was 3.5 times for cases and 3.9 times for control group. The average of abortions was 0.47 and 0.43 times for cases and control group respectively.

Table 1. General in formation of cases and control groups

Parameters	Cases n=80		Control group n=80	
	Mean	S. D	Mean	S. D
Age (years)	24.9	5.6	29.3	5.4
Gestational age (weeks)	8.7	3.2	0.0	0.0
Frequency of pregnancies	3.5	2.6	3.9	2.5
Frequency of abortions	0.47	0.88	0.43	0.91

S.D = standard deviation.

Table 2. Serum thyroid levels of thyroid hormones for pregnant ant non-pregnant women.

Hormone	Pregnant women n=80		Control group N=80		P value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
TSH (mIU/ml)	1.9	1.2	1.9	0.94	0.832
FT4 (ng/dl)	0.96	0.30	0.88	0.19	0.041
FT3 (pg/ml)	3.1	1.4	2.7	0.69	0.030

Table 3. number of cases and control group that showed elevated thyroid hormone levels:

	Pregnant women n=80 No. (%)	Control group N=80 No. (%)	Total No. (%)
TSH>5.0 mIU/ml	2(2.5)	2(2.5)	4(2.5)
FT4> 1.6 ng/dl	1(1.25)	0(0)	1(1.25)
FT3>4.7 pg/ml	11(13.75)	1(1.25)	12(7.5)

The values of assayed hormones are shown in Table 2, which shows that there was no significant difference between the means of TSH for both groups ($P>0.05$), while the mean levels of FT3 and FT4 were significantly increased in pregnant women in comparison to non-pregnant ones ($P<0.05$). Table 3 shows the number of cases and control group with elevated thyroid hormone levels

Questionnaire data revealed that the relationship between abnormal thyroid function and the presence of hereditary diseases, abnormal delivery, hypertension and age of pregnant women recruited in this study were not significant.

DISCUSSION

Maternal thyroid dysfunction and thyroid autoimmune disease in pregnancy may be associated with harmful consequences for both mother and fetus. The results of this study show a significant difference between pregnant and non-pregnant women in relation to FT4 and FT3 means. While the mean TSH level of pregnant women was lower than that of non-pregnant ones, but it did not reveal significant difference between the two groups. This finding is compatible with subclinical hyperthyroidism and it is similar to the results of other studies [12, 13].

Hypothyroidism as illustrated by elevated levels of TSH as it was observed in 2.5% of pregnant as well as non-pregnant women. This result is similar to others especially those studies which were conducted in USA and Europe [9], on the other hand, they are lower than those reported in Tunisia which were represented by 3.2% [14]. The difference between this study and others may be explained on the basis of iodine deficiency which contributes to the development of hypothyroidism [1]. It is well known that in an iodine sufficient population, thyroid function parameters in

normal pregnancies do not differ from those in non-pregnant women [9].

Another point which explains the differences among various studies are related to demographic and food habits. Other researchers reported that TSH levels during the first weeks of gestation were higher than the subsequent weeks, most probably due to the effect of high level of HCG [15, 16].

FT4 levels were high in 1.25% of the pregnant women but none in the control group. The subjects who had elevated TSH levels showed normal FT4 which indicates that they had subclinical hypothyroidism [17].

FT3 levels were above the reference limit for 13.75% and 1.25% of pregnant and non-pregnant women respectively. This finding reflects the fact that a group of pregnant women may suffer hyperthyroidism, however, as recommended by the American endocrine society, thyroid function tests during pregnancy should be interpreted cautiously as other hormones exert their effect on thyroid activity namely HCG and estrogen [15,16,17]. It is well known that high HCG levels during the first trimester has a stimulatory effect on thyroid gland, while high estrogen level is associated with transient lowering of TSH [12,18].

In conclusion, screening of thyroid function in early pregnancy should be performed to avoid future complications for both fetus and pregnant woman. The relationship between thyroid hormones and other maternal hormones should be assessed. Finally, the reference levels of TSH and its target value should be determined in all phases of pregnancy.

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